

Development of a Sustained-release System for Nitric Oxide Delivery using Alginate/Chitosan Nanoparticles

Priscyla D. Marcato^{a,b*}, Leonardo F. Adami^a, Raquel de Melo Barbosa^c, Patricia S. Melo^{c,d,e}, Iasmin R. Ferreira^d, Larissa de Paula^{c,d}, Nelson Durán^{a,c} and Amedea B. Seabra^g

^aInstituto de Química, Universidade Estadual de Campinas, C.P. 6154, Campinas, CEP 13083-970, S.P., Brazil; ^bSchool of Pharmaceutical Sciences of Ribeirão Preto, Universidade de São Paulo, Ribeirão Preto, S.P., Brazil; ^cBiochemistry Department, Institute of Biology, Universidade Estadual de Campinas, Campinas, S.P., Brazil; ^dVeris Faculdades/METROCAMP, Campinas, S.P., Brazil; ^eFaculty of Applied Sciences, Unicamp, ^fCCNH-Universidade Federal do ABC-UFABC, Santo André, S.P., Brazil; ^gUniversidade Federal de São Paulo, UNIFESP, Departamento de Ciências Exatas e da Terra, Diadema, S.P., Brazil

Abstract: Free radical nitric oxide (NO) has been known to interact with various physiological processes, such as wound repair processes and control of vascular tone. However, NO is an unstable molecule and the development of NO delivery systems that enhance its stability has also been studied. In this work, alginate/chitosan nanoparticles have been studied as a drug delivery system of the S-nitrosoglutathione (GSNO) as NO donor. For this, glutathione, GSH, the GSNO precursor, was encapsulated in alginate/chitosan nanoparticles. The presence of GSNO was confirmed by UV spectra at 336 nm. Alginate/chitosan nanoparticles with negative and positive surface charges were obtained by increasing the chitosan amount. The encapsulation efficiency (EE) relied on the nanoparticle zeta potential, obtaining 80% of EE for positive particles. The NO release from GSNO showed that polymeric nanoparticles lead to the stabilization of GSNO decomposition, at physiological temperature. Moreover, this system did not exhibit cytotoxicity for fibroblast V79 cells up to the maximum concentration tested (18 μmolL^{-1}). These results showed that alginate/chitosan nanoparticles are interesting particles to encapsulate NO donors for biomedical applications where NO might have a therapeutic effect.

Keywords: Polymeric nanoparticles, alginate, chitosan, nitric oxide, glutathione, cytotoxicity, s-nitrosoglutathione.

INTRODUCTION

Nitric oxide (NO) is characterized as an endogenous free radical that exerts an important role in different physiological processes (e.g. control of vasodilation, inhibition of platelet adhesion and aggregation, immune responses, wound healing and cellular communication) [1-5]. Exciting discoveries have demonstrated that NO is a key antimicrobial, anticancer and antioxidant agent [6-8]. Activity of NO in biological systems depends on its site, source of production, and of its concentration. Therefore, the development of NO delivery system for biomedical applications is very advantageous for the treatment of different diseases, due to the advantages of drugs encapsulated in nanostructures such as sustained release and protection of the active agent from the environment, etc. [9,10]. In addition, many classes of NO donors have been synthesized and used in biological systems [11]. In this context, the S-nitrosothiol (RSNO) class, such as, S-nitrosoglutathione (GSNO), has been highlighted. This NO donor is produced by nitrosation of glutathione (GSH), a natural peptide [12-14]. However, due to the thermal instability of RSNOs, these molecules need a vehicle to be used in pharmacological applications [11]. Thus, RSNOs and other NO donors have been administered in biopolymers or after functionalization of polymers or nanoparticles [1,15-17]. The encapsulation of drug in nanostructure is a significant subject in biomedical applications because its ability to improve the drug stability and solubility; further it also prolongs the drug release, and also decreases the toxic effect [18-20]. Different nanostructures are used as drug delivery system such as, polymeric nanoparticles, solid lipid nanoparticles, liposome, mesoporous organosilica, mesoporous carbon, carbon nanotube, etc [21, 22]. In this way, polymeric nanoparticles appear as interesting carrier systems for NO donors [23]. The encapsulation of NO donors can protect them from

degradation, direct them to specified targets and release NO over prolonged periods, enhancing its activity with low concentration [9,24].

Several papers have described the preparation of different scaffolds for NO-releasing nanomaterials, including zeolites, dendrimers, metallic and polymeric nanoparticles for several biomedical applications [17]. For example, the bactericidal effects of NO release from zeolite against Gram-negative and Gram-positive bacteria have been reported [25]. Similar results were observed for NO release from silane hydrogel containing chitosan against methicillin-resistant *staphylococcus*, on bacterial abscesses in mice [26]. Marquede-Oliveira *et al.* [27] verified that NO donor (nitrosyl ruthenium complex) encapsulated in solid lipid nanoparticles was protected until photochemical NO generation. Furthermore, the NO release was a function of temperature and time [27]. The NO donor has also been encapsulated in PLGA microparticles for the treatment of female sexual arousal disorder and tested *in vitro* in vaginal epithelial cells. The results showed that the microencapsulation protected the NO donor from degradation the acidic vaginal environment. Moreover, a sustained NO release was observed and an improvement of NO penetration through vaginal epithelial cells was also verified [28]. These examples show the advantages of NO encapsulation in nanostructures.

Other interesting nanoparticles are based on natural polymers such as alginate, chitosan, eudragit, etc. Alginate is a natural polysaccharide extracted from brown seaweed [29]. Due to its water solubility, biodegradation under normal physiological conditions, biocompatibility, and mucoadhesive characteristics, it has been widely used in several biomedical applications [30]. Similarly, chitosan, a polysaccharide obtained by deacetylation of chitin, is an attractive material for several biomedical-related applications due to

its biocompatibility, biodegradability and antibacterial actions [31,32]. Indeed, both alginate and chitosan are considered excellent biopolymers for the preparation of micro and nanoparticles [30]. Thus, due to these characteristics (biocompatibility, biodegradabil-

*Address correspondence to this author at the Faculty of Pharmaceutical Sciences of Ribeirão Preto, Universidade de São Paulo, S.P., Brazil; Tel/Fax: +55-16-3602-0490; E-mail: pmarcato@gmail.com

ity and mucoadhesive properties), in this work, these polymers (alginate and chitosan) were chosen to prepare mucoadhesive nanoparticles to encapsulate GSNO. In a preliminary communication in congress, it was observed that glutathione encapsulated in mucoadhesive polymers was able to be nitrosated and then liberate NO in a sustained way [33].

After GSH-encapsulated alginate/chitosan nanoparticles were characterized they were nitrosated to form encapsulated GSNO. The NO release from GSNO encapsulated in alginate/chitosan nanoparticles was followed at 37°C and compared to free GSNO, under the same conditions. Furthermore, a cytotoxic study was carried out to evaluate the biomedical potential of this system.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

Chitosan (105 kDa / ~81% acetylation) was obtained from Polymar, Ciência e Nutrição S/A, Fortaleza, CE, Brazil. HCl was from Synth, Brazil. Alginate (~250 cps), glutathione (g-Glu-Cys-Glu, GSH), sodium nitrite, 5,5-dithiobis(2-nitrobenzoic acid) (DTNB), acetic acid, and phosphate buffer saline (PBS), pH 7.4, were obtained from Sigma, St. Louis, MO, USA and were used as received. All aqueous solutions were prepared using analytical grade water from a Millipore Milli-Q Gradient filtration system. Dulbecco's modified Eagle's medium (DMEM), fetal bovine serum, penicillin and streptomycin were obtained from Nutricell, Campinas, SP, Brazil. Methylthiazolotetrazolium and neutral red dye were also obtained from Sigma.

Polymeric GSH Nanoparticles Synthesis

The ionic gelation method for alginate/chitosan nanoparticles containing GSH was used (modified from ref. [34]). Briefly, chitosan solution (1.33% in water) with GSH, (3.5-25 mg) was prepared. This solution (0.5 or 1 mL) was dropped into an alginate solution (50 µg mL⁻¹) at pH 4.0 under stirring, to obtain two different ratios of alginate/chitosan solutions: 1.5 and 0.75.

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

Particles were characterized by scanning electron microscopy (Jeol JSM-6360LV) at a voltage of 20 kV after prior coating with gold/palladium under vacuum by sputtering using a BAL-TEC apparatus. Secondary electron images were obtained.

Alginate/Chitosan Nanoparticles with and without GSH: Physical Characterization

The average size and size distribution of prepared nanoparticles of 0.75 and 1.5 alginate/chitosan ratios with and without GSH were measured by photon correlation spectroscopy (PCS) (Nano ZS Zetasizer, Malvern Instruments Corp) at 25°C in polystyrene cuvettes, with a path length of 10 mm. The zeta potential was measured in capillary cells with path lengths of 10 mm, using the Nano ZS Zetasizer. Measurements were performed with a solution of 0.1 mmol L⁻¹ sodium chloride.

Stability of the Alginate/Chitosan Nanoparticles

The physical stabilities of alginate/chitosan nanoparticles with 1.5 and 0.75 ratios, with GSH or without GSH, were analyzed by PCS, as described previously. During 35 days, the dispersion was kept at low temperature (4 °C) and followed the particle sizes and surface charges.

GSH Encapsulation Efficiency in Alginate/Chitosan Nanoparticles

The GSH encapsulation efficiency was measured by the UV-Vis method described in the literature [35]. Initially, no encapsulated GSH was separated from polymeric nanoparticles by ultracentrifugation. For this, 500 µL of GSH encapsulated in polymeric nanoparticles was filtered in a Microcon centrifugal filter device

containing ultrafiltration membranes (MWCO 10,000, Millipore). The amount of free GSH in the ultrafiltrates was measured by the 5,5'-dithiobis-(2-nitrobenzoic acid) (DTNB) reaction, based on the absorbance at 412 nm ($E = 14.15 \text{ mmolL}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$) of the 2-nitro-5-thiobenzoate anion, which is generated in the reaction of GSH with DTNB [35]. A volume of 0.5 mL of ultrafiltered GSH was added to 0.5 mL of 12 mmolL⁻¹ of DTNB in PBS buffer (pH 7.4), after 5 min of incubation the absorbance at 412 nm was measured in a UV-VIS Agilent® 8453 spectrophotometer (SIGMA-D8130). The percentage of GSH encapsulation was determined by the described equation:

$$(\%) = (\text{mass of GSH encapsulated} / \text{mass of GSH total}) \times 100$$

Influence of pH on Diameter and Zeta Potential of GSH-containing Alginate/Chitosan Nanoparticles

The influence of pH from 4.00 to 10.0 on diameter and zeta potential of GSH-containing alginate/chitosan nanoparticles was determined with a MTP-2 Multi Purpose Titrator (Malvern®) coupled to the Malvern®. Zeta Sizer.

Nitrosation of GSH/Alginate/Chitosan Nanoparticles

25 mg of GSH (400 µmolL⁻¹) encapsulated in 0.75 alginate/chitosan nanoparticles ratio was nitrosated by 1:1 amounts of sodium nitrite directly into a polymeric aqueous dispersion (pH 4.0). The final solution was mixed with a magnetic stirrer for 40 min, using an ice bath and protected from light. Formation of GSNO/alginate/chitosan nanoparticles was characterized by the absorption band of the S-NO group (336 nm_{max} ($E = 940 \text{ molL}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$), using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer [35].

Similarly, free GSH (25 mg; 400 µmolL⁻¹) in aqueous acidified solution (pH 4.0) was nitrosated by adding 1:1 amounts of sodium nitrite, as described earlier, obtaining free GSNO in aqueous solution.

Kinetic Measurements of GSNO Decomposition with NO re-release from Encapsulated GSNO and Free GSNO at Physiological Temperature

The kinetic curves of GSNO (400 µmolL⁻¹) decomposition with NO release were monitored at 336 nm for either free GSNO (aqueous solution) or encapsulated one in alginate/chitosan nanoparticles (ratio 0.75). Kinetic data were taken at this wavelength at 30 min intervals at 37 °C for 21 h. The amount of NO released from free and encapsulated GSNO was calculated directly from the amount of GSNO decomposition, as previously described [36]. Each point of the kinetic curves represents the average of three independent experiments, with the error bars expressed by the standard error of the mean. NO release rates from GSNO decomposition were obtained by linear regression of the slopes of the curves.

Mathematical Modeling of the Release Experiments

The results of drug release profiles from nanoparticles can allow important details about the release mechanism of active compound engaged. A new mathematical model has been proposed and this favors the understanding of the phenomena involved in drug delivery and adjustment of data with greater accuracy [37]. Korsmeyer-Peppas model (Eq. 1), a semi-empirical model, was applied to the GSNO release curves in order to identify the type of mechanism involved [38].

$$M(t)/M_w = kt^n \tag{Eq. 1}$$

With, M_t represented amount of GSNO releases at time t , M_w total amount of GSNO releases at time t , K is a constant that considers structural and geometrical aspects of the system, and the value of the exponent (n) is used to characterize the release mechanism. The release exponent (n), according to Korsmeyer-Peppas, can be characterized by three different mechanisms (Fickian, anomalous, or Type II transport), when $n < 0.43$ the release is di-

rected by classical Fickian diffusion, $n > 0.85$ governed by Type II transport, involving polymer swelling and relaxation of the polymeric matrix and n between 0.43 and 0.85 shows anomalous transport kinetics, with a combination of the two diffusion mechanisms and Type II transport [39].

Cytotoxicity of Free and Encapsulated GSNO in Nanoparticles

The cytotoxicities of GSNO, both free and encapsulated in 0.75 alginate/chitosan nanoparticles ratio, were measured in a Chinese hamster lung fibroblast cell line (V79) culture [40]. V79 fibroblasts were grown as monolayers in Dulbecco's modified Eagle's medium (DMEM) supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum, 100 IU of penicillin/ml and 100 Ag of streptomycin/ml in a humidified incubator with 5% CO₂ in air at 37 °C. The cells were plated in 96-well plates (density of 3×10^4 cells/ml). Forty-eight hours after this process, semiconfluent cultures were exposed to free and encapsulated GSNO (0-18 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ concentration). The compounds were studied after exposing the cells for 24 h to the test medium with or without control. In three experiments, each concentration was tested in six replicates. After incubation time the MTT and neutral red uptake assay were evaluated.

Endpoint Tests for Cytotoxicity

Neutral red Uptake

The neutral red uptake was measured by the method of Borefreund and Puermer (1984) [41]. Briefly, cells were washed once with PBS after removal of the culture medium. After 4 h of incubation with serum-free medium containing neutral red (50 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$), the cells were washed in PBS, followed by the addition of 0.1 ml of a solution of 1% acetic acid and ethanol (50%) to each well to fix the cells and to remove the neutral red from the solution. The plates were shaken gently for 20 min on a plate shaker, and the absorbance of the solution was read at 540 nm (VersaMaxk, Tunable Microplate Reader, Molecular Devices, Co., Sunnyvale, CA, USA).

Methylthiazoletetrazolium (MTT) Reduction

The MTT reduction assay was performed as described by Denizot and Lang [42]. Briefly, cells were washed once with PBS before adding 0.1 ml of serum-free medium containing 0.05% of MTT salt to each well. After incubation for 5 h, the culture medium was removed, and 0.1 ml of ethanol was added to each well to solubilize the formazan formed. The plates were shaken gently for 10 min and the absorbance was measured at 570 nm (VersaMaxk, Tunable Microplate Reader).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

GSN/alginate/Chitosan Nanoparticles Preparation

Nanoparticles of 1.5 Alginate/Chitosan Ratio

Preparation of 1.5 alginate/chitosan ratios with GSH and without GSH, gave an average diameters of 212 and 217 nm, respectively (Table 1). The zeta potential was negative and the value did

not change significantly with GSH encapsulation (Table 1). This negative value can be explained by considering the higher concentration of alginate compared with chitosan. Table 1 shows that both average diameters and the surface charges of the nanoparticles were not significantly changed upon encapsulation of GSH into the polymeric nanoparticles. However, efficiency of encapsulation of GSH into 1.5 alginate/chitosan ratio was only 1.0% (Table 1).

Nanoparticles of Alginate/Chitosan 0.75 Ratio

Preparation of 0.75 alginate/chitosan nanoparticles ratio with and without GSH gave particles sizes of around 361 and 301 nm, respectively, and positive surface charges values of +27 (with GSH) and + 22 mV (without GSH) (Table 1). The positive potential indicates the presence of chitosan on the particle surfaces. This alteration improved the encapsulation efficiency to 80% showing to be better particles for GSH encapsulation than the particles prepared with the 1.5 alginate/chitosan ratio.

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

Fig. (1) shows the scanning electronic microscopy (SEM) of the 0.75 alginate/chitosan nanoparticles ratio with GSH. The non spherical particle shapes were observed which might be due to the dry process for the SEM analysis.

Physical Stability of Alginate/Chitosan Nanoparticles

Fig. (2) shows the variation of nanoparticle average sizes and PdI for nanoparticles of alginate/chitosan at 1.5 and at 0.75 ratios without GSH for 35 days at 4 °C. The positively charged particles exhibit higher stability than the negatively charged particles, as shown in Fig. (2). After 35 days, the diameter of the negatively charged particles increased by 51% while the positive particle diameter increased by only 16% ($n = 3$) confirming that positive nanoparticles are better carriers than the negative nanoparticles.

Influence of pH on Diameter and Zeta Potential of Alginate/Chitosan Nanoparticles

In term of stability alginate/chitosan/GSH nanoparticles at different pHs was studied. Fig. (3A) shows the dependence of both particle size and zeta potential of alginate/chitosan/GSH nanoparticle (0.75 alginate:chitosan ratio) with pH. It can be observed that the increase of the pH (from 5 to 10) caused particles aggregation (particle sizes increased 300%). Furthermore, the zeta potential changed from positive (+ 17 mV) to negative (-33 mV) values by increasing the pH (Fig. 3A). However, for alginate/chitosan nanoparticles with GSH (ratio of alginate:chitosan 1.5) a smaller increase in particle size (163%) was observed with the increase in the pH, and the zeta potential decreased from -3 mV to -10 mV (Fig. 3B). In both cases, particle agglomeration was observed when the solution pH was similar to the chitosan pKa (~ 6.5). These results demonstrate that the surface properties of nanoparticles are predominantly governed by chitosan content.

Table 1. Zeta Potential (Surface Charge), Particles Sizes, and Encapsulation Efficiency of Alginate/Chitosan Nanoparticles in Three Different Ratios with and without GSH

Alginate/Chitosan ratios	GSH (mg)	Zeta Potential (mV)	Particles sizes (nm)	PdI (polydispersity index)	Encapsulation efficiency (%)
0.750	0.0	+ 22	300.8	0.316	-
0.750	5.0	+ 27	361.4	0.330	80
1.500	0.0	- 20	217.0	0.413	-
1.500	3.5	- 23	211.6	0.400	1

Fig. (1). SEM images of 0.75 alginate/chitosan/GSH nanoparticles ratio.

Fig. (2). Stability of alginate/chitosan nanoparticles at 1.5 and 0.75 ratios, without GSH at 4 °C for 35 days after preparation.

Fig. (3). Influence of pH on particle size (-■-) and on zeta potential (-○-) of alginate/chitosan/GSH nanoparticles. Alginate:chitosan ratio of: **A)** 1.5 and **B)** 0.75.

Nitrosation of Alginate/Chitosan/GSH Nanoparticles

Fig. (4) shows the ultraviolet spectra of alginate/chitosan nanoparticles containing GSH before and after nitrosation. In this figure, the band characteristic of GSNO at 336 nm can be observed after the reaction with sodium nitrite and the absence of this band before the reaction. This results shows that encapsulated GSH is readily nitrosated to GSNO inside the alginate/chitosan nanoparti-

cles. Therefore, GSNO can be prepared from alginate/chitosan/GSH suspension by nitrosation of GSH in the nanoparticles.

Kinetics of NO Release from Free GSNO and GSNO Encapsulated in Polymeric Nanoparticles

In Fig. (5), it is possible to see the kinetic curves of NO release for free GSNO and encapsulated GSNO (0.75 alginate/chitosan/GSNO nanoparticles ratio) for 21 h at 37° at pH 4.0. NO is spontaneously released from free and encapsulated GSNO through ther-

Fig. (4). Ultraviolet spectra of 0.75 alginate/chitosan/GSH nanoparticles ratio ($400 \mu\text{molL}^{-1}$ GSH) at pH 4.0: (a) before addition of nitrite and (b) after addition of equimolar amounts of nitrite.

Fig. (5). Kinetic curves of NO released from GSNO ($400 \mu\text{molL}^{-1}$) at 37°C for 21 h at pH 4: (a) free GSNO; (b) GSNO encapsulated in 0.75 alginate/chitosan nanoparticles ratio.

mally S-N bond cleavage (hemolytic), with the concomitant formation of oxidized glutathione, according to Equation 2 [36]:

The release of GSNO from alginate/chitosan nanoparticles depends on various mechanisms, such as desorption, diffusion, particle erosion or the combination of these factors including desorption from the surface, diffusion through the pores or wall and disintegration, dissolution or erosion of the hydropolymeric structure [43-45]. It can be observed that the rate of NO release is greatly reduced for encapsulated GSNO (curve b) compared with free GSNO (curve a). Indeed, the rates of NO release were found to be 12.5 ± 0.11 and $0.46 \pm 0.07 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$ for free and encapsulated GSNO, respectively. This data clearly indicated that the alginate/chitosan/GSNO nanoparticles can decrease 27-fold the rates of NO release from GSNO at 37°C . Moreover, after 21 h at 37°C , 62% of NO was released from free GSNO, in contrast, only 3% of NO was released from encapsulated GSNO.

The release profile data were treated using the Korsmeyer-Peppas model (Fig. 6) in order to obtain the values of the release constant (K) and the exponent (n) (Table 2) and identification of drug release mechanisms from nanostructured systems [38,43]. The

value of n was 0.35, indicating that the release mechanism involved a classical Fickian diffusion. The value of K was 1.306 min^{-1} and the fitting observed was 0.9046.

These results show that the encapsulation of the NO donor into nanoparticles can be used to control NO release for longer durations, by greatly decreasing the rates of thermal GSNO decomposition with consequent NO release. This fact can be explained due to the low diffusion rates of the encapsulated GSNO nanoparticles to the aqueous solution.

It must be noted that the biological actions of NO depend on the flux of NO released. Lower NO concentrations, in the range of nanomolar are required for the therapeutic effects of NO, such as the increasing of blood flow and promotion of wound healing [4,17], whereas, higher amounts of NO released have bacterial, viricidal, leishmanicidal and tumoricidal activities [17,46]. The amount of GSNO encapsulated into alginate/chitosan nanoparticles can be adjusted to the desired biomedical application. A kinetic profile of NO release, as shown in Fig. (5b), can be used for biological applications (wound healing or platelet adhesion and aggregation inhibition). In both cases, micromolar amounts of NO are required to be released for long periods of time [17].

Fig. (6). Results obtained using the Korsmeyer-Peppas mathematical model applied to GSNO encapsulated in alginate/chitosan nanoparticle.

Table 2. Values of the Release Constant (K), Exponent (n) and Correlation Coefficient (r), for the GSNO Encapsulated in Alginate/Chitosan Nanoparticles

Sample	K(min ⁻¹)	n	r
GSNO encapsulated in alginate/chitosan nanoparticles	1.306	0.3508	0.9046

Cytotoxicity Study

Free GSNO did not show cytotoxicity to fibroblast V79 cells in the Neutral red assay (lysosomal) and was slightly cytotoxic in the MTT assay (mitochondrial) (20% at around 16 μmolL^{-1} , as is observed in Fig. (7)). Similarly, it was reported that GSNO decreased neutrophil viability as followed by a fluorescent viability/cytotoxicity assay. In this case a time and concentration-dependent manner was observed [47].

None of alginate/chitosan nanoparticles exhibited cytotoxicity to fibroblast V79 cells (up to 18 μmolL^{-1} concentration). This means that the slight cytotoxicity observed for free GSNO was completely eliminated by its incorporation in alginate/chitosan nanoparticles (Fig. 7). Similar results were reported by Hetrick *et al.*, (2008) [48], in which NO-releasing silica nanoparticles were found to be nontoxic to mammalian fibroblast cells, at concentra-

tions able to kill bacteria, while the free NO donor exhibited a significant toxicity to fibroblast cells.

CONCLUSIONS

GSH encapsulated into biodegradable alginate/chitosan nanoparticles can be readily nitrosated leading to the formation of GSNO in the nanoparticles. The rates of NO release from GSNO are greatly reduced due to GSNO encapsulation into biodegradable and non-toxic nanoparticles. Furthermore, the GSNO encapsulation decreased the cytotoxic effect of GSNO in fibroblast V79 cells. Thus, the better stability of encapsulated GSNO compared to free GSNO and the absence of cytotoxicity of alginate/chitosan/GSNO nanoparticles enables the use this new NO-nanocarrier in pharmaceutical applications, or other uses where the NO effects are required, without severe side effects.

Fig. (7). Cell viability of V79 fibroblast treated with: a) free GSNO, b) alginate/chitosan (ratio of 0.75), c) GSNO encapsulated in alginate/chitosan (ratio of 0.75).

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors confirm that this article content has no conflicts of interest.

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